

D3.3 Engagement Services Status

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

BoF	Birds of a Feather
CoP	Community of Practice
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
HEIs	Higher Education Institutions
IG	Interest Group
RDA	Research Data Alliance
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This deliverable represents the first update of the engagement component of the RDA TIGER Landscape & Engagement service. Following on from 'D3.1 Engagement Services Service Update' this report describes how the RDA TIGER project has provided its supported WGs with engagement services over the first two years of the project. Included here is an outline of the types of engagement strategies co-developed by the RDA TIGER project partners and WG co-chairs, the factors influencing these, and the associated tasks and activities used to execute these strategies. Also described is the overlapping nature of RDA TIGER support services and how these influence the engagement activities.

Based on the key performance indicators and the feedback gathered so far in the project, the engagement component of the RDA TIGER Landscape & Engagement service has been a success. The project overall is on track or has already met various KPIs. A key aim for the final year of the project is for the various support services to work more in concert with one another in order to maximise the impact that the project itself and the outputs of its supported WGs have.

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1. Introduction

This deliverable examines the engagement strategies and activities developed by the RDA TIGER project as part of the project’s Landscape & Engagement Service for RDA Working Groups (WGs). At this point in the project (approximately two years since the project began, with one year remaining) the engagement activities carried out by the project have reached a level of maturity, and have been employed in a large number of instances, such that they can be codified and evaluated effectively. This deliverable follows on from D3.2 Engagement Services Service Update¹, which set out the scope of the engagement support that was available to RDA TIGER-supported WGs and contained suggestions for how the service might develop throughout the project. This report then represents the synthesis of initial description of the engagement service and attendant activities, and their execution in practice.

At the time of writing, the RDA TIGER project has supported 22 RDA WGs with in-kind support services (see Table 1. below); depending on the stage of the WG at the commencement of RDA TIGER support, each of these WGs have benefited from the engagement support provided by the Landscape & Engagement Service to some degree. What is clear at this stage of the project, and is explained in more detail in other relevant RDA TIGER deliverables², is that there is significant overlap between the engagement component of the Landscape & Engagement service and other RDA TIGER services, especially the Communications and Facilitation Services. It is more often the case than not that there is not a specific member of the RDA TIGER project partners assigned to assist a WG with engagement alone; as each WG’s engagement strategy and activities are linked to its overall aims, it is more often than not the case that the individual assigned to the WG from the RDA TIGER Facilitation Service will provide engagement support, or, in cases where only Communications Service support has been applied for, the individual assigned to the WG from the RDA TIGER Communications Service.

Table 1. Overview of Working Groups support commencement stages

Total WGs supported with in-kind support	22
• Total WG supported from WG initiation period (including Statement of Work development)	14
• Total WGs supported from WG activity period (i.e., after RDA Council endorsement)	4

¹ Rettberg, N., & Asmi, A. (2023). D3.2 Engagement Services Service Update (1.2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10444701>

² See for example: Delipalta, A. (2023). RDA TIGER D2.2: Updated Plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7991152>; O’Connor, R. (2024). D5.2 First Evaluation of the Facilitation Services. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12599362>; and Rettberg, N., Asmi, A., Molloy, L., Hugo, W., Delipalta, A., & Saldner, S. (2023). RDA TIGER D3.1 OS Landscape analysis and potential engagement targets. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8096612>.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Total WG supported from finalisation period (i.e., concluding WG outputs, supporting adoption, etc.) 	4
WGs developing from a previous initiative (i.e., previous RDA Group or outside initiative)	11
WGs addressing a new topic	11

As will become clear below, there is a wide degree of variety in terms of the engagement strategies and activities available to each of the RDA TIGER-supported WGs, as well as in the levels of responsibility for decisions to do with engagement. This report then gives an update on how the engagement service has been delivered in practice, parsing the types of strategies employed by WGs at different stages of their lifecycles and the activities used to support these strategies. The report will later examine the information collection tasks taking place to support the engagement service and how the service has been measured at this stage against the relevant project key performance indicators (KPIs).

2. Overview of engagement strategies

The overall goal of the engagement component of the Landscape & Engagement Service is to identify and make meaningful connections with individuals, groups and organisations relevant to RDA TIGER-supported WGs, on a continuing basis at all stages of WG activity (see section 2 of D3.2 Engagement Services Service Update³). In this section, the report will look at the engagement strategies that RDA TIGER-supported WGs can employ (including examples of how they have been employed and the factors influencing them). Then in Section 3 below the report will outline the activities implemented in support of these strategies.

As with all RDA WGs, individuals are free to join RDA TIGER-supported WGs at any stage of its lifecycle (see Figure 1. below); however, in order to ensure that the WG has sufficient input into its workplan and that its planned outputs are relevant to all of its identified target audiences, the majority of engagement activities need to be carried out at the early stages of the WG (that is, as part of the WG set-up and Statement of Work development phases, and in the first few months after RDA Council endorsement). The engagement strategy for each WG therefore needs to take into account these two factors: one, that it is beneficial for the WG to actively engage with and onboard as many WG members as possible as early as possible, and; two, that engagement should be treated as an ongoing activity.

³ Rettberg, N., & Asmi, A. (2023). D3.2 Engagement Services Service Update (1.2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10444701>.

Figure 1. RDA WG vs RDA TIGER life cycle stages

Within RDA TIGER-supported WGs, the engagement strategy is typically developed by the RDA TIGER facilitator and the WG co-chairs. Depending on the stage of the WG, the facilitator and co-chairs will assess the WG's current engagement requirements and decide on an appropriate engagement strategy. As with other aspects of RDA TIGER support services (i.e., Facilitation, Communications, etc.) it is at the discretion of WG co-chairs how 'hands-on' they should be in terms of the practical tasks to do with WG support; in the case of engagement, it may be the case that co-chairs have a clear idea of target individuals and/or organisations they want to engage with at each stage of the WG lifecycle, or they may need guidance from the facilitator on this. At any stage of the WG lifecycle, a Landscape Analysis report can be requested, which can supplement engagement efforts by mapping to similar initiatives or potential interested parties on the subject matter of the WG. Similarly, when it comes to the practical aspects of outreach (i.e., getting in contact with these engagement targets) it may be that the co-chairs prefer to contact them directly, or prefer for the facilitator to do it on their behalf (or some cases, to divide this work up, depending on the target).

Responsibility for the development and execution of the WG's engagement strategy is shared by the WG co-chairs and the main point of contact with RDA TIGER (typically the facilitator). A key point to note here is that the engagement strategy will depend on both the stage of the WG (these stages are explained in more detail below), the type of engagement strategy the co-chairs envisage, and the advice and support available from RDA TIGER. Though these factors can be described separately, as with the delivery of the RDA TIGER services, there is no 'one-size-fits-all' approach to how a WG's engagement strategy is developed and how the subsequent actions are carried out.

2.1 Engagement strategy stages

The different stages of a WG's lifecycle and the specific engagement strategies required are outlined below, each detailing the reason for, and goals of, engagement at each stage.

2.1.a. Group initiation

The support provided by RDA TIGER at the WG initiation period is contingent on the level of maturity and how developed the Statement of Work for the WG at this early stage. Some WGs who are supported by RDA TIGER arise from previous or ongoing initiatives (e.g., follow on WGs, spin-out WGs from RDA IGs, extensions of other projects, etc.) and as such will have already engaged with a lot of their target audiences and stakeholders; in these cases, the engagement strategy will focus on ensuring momentum for the WG as it goes through the Statement of Work development, review and endorsement stages, where it is necessary to identify additional parties whose presence would be of benefit to the WG or who may be the target audience of the WG's planned outputs. Co-chairs will typically set the engagement strategy in these cases, recruiting WG members from existing contacts and based on their knowledge of the communities and landscapes of relevance to the WG. The role of the facilitator here is to provide support, but mainly to carry out any practical engagement activities related to the engagement strategy.

As the RDA TIGER project does not use the experience of applicants with RDA and RDA processes as a criteria for evaluating support applications, in many cases the project has provided support to WGs whose co-chairs are new members of RDA or have no prior experience of co-chairing an RDA Group of any type. In these cases, the engagement strategy will need to be co-developed by the WG's prospective co-chairs and RDA TIGER. The WG co-chairs will have a good understanding of the topic that the WG is focusing on and the relevant landscape, and will thus have an idea of what the most appropriate individuals or communities to engage with. The facilitator can assist here (supplemented by a Landscape Awareness report if necessary, and the Welcome Pack developed by the Facilitation Service⁴) in providing links to relevant initiatives within RDA or in RDA TIGER consortium partner activities, especially with respect to cross-cutting themes (e.g., interoperability, metadata standards, ethics, etc.).

In both cases - where a WG is developing from a previous initiative(s) or where it is addressing a new topic (see Table 1. above) - the need to satisfy the RDA criteria for a WG to have geographical diversity of co-chairs need to be addressed. In many cases of RDA TIGER-supported WGs, the engagement service is required to help identify and recruit additional co-chairs for the WG. This requires a specific form of engagement as it differs from WG member engagement in that becoming a co-chair brings with it a level of responsibility to contribute to the WG's activities and overall direction⁵. The strategy for co-chair engagement requires the existing co-chair(s) to work with the facilitator to identify what additional experience or expertise the WG needs, and to then compile a shortlist of individuals to approach. Again, this initial contact can be made by one of the co-chairs or the facilitator, and will typically outline to the prospective co-chair the WG's aims, why they are being approached to become a co-chair, what is required in the role (if they are not already familiar), and how the RDA TIGER project can support them.

⁴ Welcome Pack - an onboarding guide for RDA Working Groups:

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1i1F-xMwTv3ZxPxNBBzdDGisUZhqFas4t/view?usp=drive_link

⁵ RDA Group Chairs Roles and Responsibilities:

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/group-chair-responsibilities/>

2.1.b. Statement of Work development

At this stage, the overall aims of the WG are elaborated according to the process to which all RDA WGs must adhere⁶. The development and writing of the Statement of Work is led by the co-chairs along with any WG members who have joined at this early stage (a key thing to note here is that the development or writing of the Statement of Work is not the responsibility of the RDA TIGER facilitator, though they can advise on how it responds to the criteria by which the RDA Technical Advisory Board will evaluate it and offer guidance on what type of information is required in specific sections). The engagement strategy here will focus on ensuring that there is active contribution to the Statement of Work, not only from the co-chairs already in place, but also from any additional WG members whose input is required to ensure that the WG comprehensively achieves its activities and its planned outcomes.

In addition, the engagement strategy focuses on giving new WG members (and new co-chairs, if necessary) the opportunity to shape the direction of the WG before it is officially endorsed. It is key to identify and engage with individuals whose work directly aligns with the WG's activities or will benefit from its outputs. As such, all engagement activities at this stage, whether direct one-to-one engagement with new or existing contacts or invitations to 'kick-off' meetings or writing sessions, need to communicate the value of becoming a WG member at this stage and how contributing to the development of the Statement of Work can ensure that the WG's activities and outputs are as impactful as possible for the WG's target audiences.

2.1.c. Statement of Work Community Review

As part of the process to endorse a new RDA WG, it is a requirement to open the Statement of Work for Community Review. This means publishing the Statement of Work in the RDA website and inviting comments and feedback from RDA members. Concurrently, the RDA TAB carries out its own review of the document, providing its own feedback. In terms of the engagement strategy, it is possible for new WG's to take a reactive stance to this, responding to feedback as it is received, or as a whole at the end of the Community Review period. However, the support provided by RDA TIGER allows its WGs to be more proactive; in addition to the regular communications channels used to promote all Statements of Work in Community Review, the RDA TIGER Engagement and Communications Services help in disseminating the Statement of Work to groups and communities of relevance, using it as a means to recruit new WG members. Having a first version of the Statement of Work available, which elaborates the WG's intentions, allows potential members to have more clarity on how they may be able to contribute to the WG, rather than joining and contributing to these discussions at an earlier stage.

⁶ RDA WG Statement of Work development:
<https://www.rd-alliance.org/wg-case-statement-development/>

2.1.d. Ongoing WG recruitment and onboarding

After the initial stages of WG formation and the official kick-off of activities, there is a continuous effort to build WG membership. This ensures a plurality and diversity of voices and maintains a sufficient number of active and engaged members to execute the WG's work plan. Furthermore, as the work progresses, additional expertise may be needed, making recruitment beyond the initial stages crucial to provide the necessary skills and perspectives across the membership.

To this end, the RDA TIGER facilitator assists the group in identifying any gaps in membership and supports efforts to recruit members with relevant expertise, both within and outside the RDA communities. Additionally, the facilitator ensures the smooth and efficient onboarding of new members, helping them become familiar with the WG's activities to date, the timeline of remaining WG activities and milestones, and providing advice and support in navigating RDA processes if necessary.

2.1.e Periodic WG outreach

As part of the engagement strategy for each WG, specific activities outlined in the Statement of Work or agreed upon after the WG is endorsed and begins its work may require targeted engagement with key stakeholder groups. These activities may include (but are not limited to):

- **Surveys:** Distributed to relevant communities to collect diverse input that shapes WG deliverables. (WG surveys supported: 3)
- **Structured interviews:** Conducted with key stakeholders or experts to gain in-depth perspectives on specific data challenges or solutions developed within the WG. (WG structured interviews supported: none to date)
- **Workshops and events:** Organised as open or closed sessions to 'kick-off' WGs, present interim findings, gather actionable feedback, and to refine ongoing efforts. (Workshops and events supported: 9)
- **Stakeholder Consultations:** Targeted outreach to expert groups, or as part of community consultation, ensuring inclusivity and relevance in shaping outputs (stakeholder consultations supported: 7).

The RDA TIGER facilitator supports the group in engaging with their target audiences to ensure the relevance and impact of the feedback. The RDA TIGER Communications service supports these engagement activities, along with the facilitator helping to promote and disseminate these activities internally, through the RDA website, and externally, using RDA communication channels. Dissemination efforts include leveraging RDA's website, newsletters, social media channels, and external platforms when appropriate. The collaboration between the facilitator and the communication team ensures that messages are clear, well-targeted, and effectively delivered, driving engagement that aligns with the WG's objectives.

2.1.f. Final WG engagement

During the final stages of a WG's lifecycle, RDA TIGER provides robust support through its Facilitation, Communication, Landscape & Engagement, and Output support services⁷, ensuring that all work delivered by the RDA WGs meets community needs and has a sustainable impact. During the Community Review phase for its proposed Recommendation(s)⁸, the RDA TIGER facilitator promotes WG outputs within RDA and externally to gather feedback essential for shaping the final Recommendation(s). Facilitators also help WGs devise targeted engagement plans to ensure outputs are shared effectively with key stakeholders, aligning dissemination efforts with the WG's goals.

After the official endorsement of the Recommendation by the RDA Council, RDA TIGER supports the adoption and impact of outputs through tailored communication efforts, such as infographics, leaflets, and brochures, which are designed to amplify their reach and influence. Examples include brochures targeting two different intended audience groups of the GORC Model WG^{9, 10} and a visual and a brochure outlining the key findings of the National PID Strategies WG^{11, 12}. Again, this is an area where communications and engagement activities overlap and complement one another; in the cases above, for example, the materials produced in coordination with the Communications Service have supported the engagement strategies of each WG, promoting the outputs of the WGs to potential adopters.

Where necessary, the facilitator also works with the co-chairs and/or deliverable authors to identify any organisations that may need to be engaged to support the longer-term impact and sustainability of the WG's outputs. For example, a WG producing a Recommendation for a specific metadata standard may need to engage with and collaborate with a repository service provider to implement its Recommendations; similarly, a WG producing a Recommendation for policies may need to engage with research policies bodies or research funders to ensure that their work is impactful beyond the end of the WG's lifespan. RDA TIGER can here support the WG and co-chairs to develop a strategy to engage with any relevant stakeholders who may be key in ensuring that the work done by the WG has maximum impact.

⁷ Description of RDA TIGER services: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/rda-tiger-services/>

⁸ RDA Working Group Recommendations & Supporting Outputs – related processes and submission guidelines:

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/recommendations-amp-supporting-outputs-related-processes-and-submission-guidelines/>

⁹ Delipalta, A. (2023). Global Open Research Commons International Model RDA Working Group: Considerations for Developing Policy with Global Impact. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14341560>

¹⁰ Delipalta, A. (2023). Global Open Research Commons International Model Working Group: Adopting and Implementing the Model for your organisation. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14341230>

¹¹ Delipalta, A. (2023). Global Open Research Commons International Model Working Group: Adopting and Implementing the Model for your organisation. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14341230>

¹² Delipalta, A. (2023). National PID Strategies: What, why, how - and where next?. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14340813>

To ensure WG outputs themselves remain accessible beyond the WG's lifecycle, RDA TIGER Outputs Support service is developing the RDA Knowledge Base¹³. The Knowledge Base is the central point for searching and retrieving RDA outputs and supporting materials, improving their discoverability and fostering continued stakeholder engagement. By curating outputs and contextual resources, the RDA Knowledge Base not only enhances visibility but also supports their long-term sustainability and usability. Once this is operational, the improved discoverability of RDA Group outputs will need to be factored into future engagement strategies. This is another example of the complementary nature of the RDA TIGER services and how developments in one service (i.e. development of the Knowledge Base) can positively influence another (i.e., allowing the engagement strategy to be more impactful)./

3. Engagement activities

This section describes the practical activities that RDA TIGER-supported WGs can use to implement their engagement strategies. Again, as above, there is overlap between the engagement component of the Landscape & Engagement Service and the Facilitation and Communications Services in how the tasks and activities described below are delivered. Outside of the landscape analysis task, the activities described below are ones that all RDA WGs carry out in some capacity; the advantage for the WG of having RDA TIGER support is that there is dedicated resource available to the WG for these activities to be carried out, as well as the experience of the RDA TIGER project partners to be able to recommend specific tasks or activities, depending on the WG's needs.

3.1 Landscape analysis

Via the RDA TIGER Landscape & Engagement Service, supported WGs can request a Landscape Analysis report. WG co-chairs, supported by their RDA TIGER facilitators, contact the Landscape & Engagement Service with a request for a Landscape Analysis report. The request is discussed in the project's WP3; based on available resources and knowledge of the WG's field, an author for the report is assigned. The scope of the report is defined by the assigned author, the WP3 lead, the WG co-chairs, and (where necessary) the RDA TIGER facilitator. Production of this report is typically based on desk research as well as engagement with RDA TIGER partners' extensive networks. This work results in a landscape report prepared for the commissioning WG. Such landscape analysis supports WGs in identifying relevant stakeholders for their WG as well as current and past projects in the domain of the WG, and particularly in related domains. This supports the WGs engagement with all relevant stakeholders, also those beyond the immediate networks of the groups' co-chairs and members, throughout the life cycle of the working groups and supports greater impact of WG outputs.

¹³ Hugo, W. (2024). D4.2 – Description of Output Support Services and Maintenance Platform (1.0.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12568754>. Note that the term 'Maintenance Platform' has been updated to 'Knowledge Base' since the publication of this deliverable.

The RDA TIGER Facilitation Service, specifically the TIGER facilitators assigned to RDA TIGER-supported WGs also engage in ongoing landscape analysis for the WGs that they work with. This ongoing landscape analysis is less formal than the landscape work provided by the RDA TIGER Landscape Service and happens at ad hoc basis, as result from facilitators' conversations with co-chairs and participation in WGs working meetings. Facilitators do not produce formal reports of such landscape work, which rather feeds into direct communication, communication and dissemination activities that are described below.

3.2 Communications, outreach and dissemination

From the Communications perspective (WP2) and in order to meaningfully separate the tasks, services and overall division of labour across the WPs and the Consortium, 'engagement' has been defined as the point in time where a successful communications activity or campaign has attracted new WG members or new service users, and these new members or service users are now able to further engage with the project's services, results, and service providers (WP leads, facilitators). This is an important distinction to avoid confusion between the multiple community-facing activities carried out by the project (service awareness and general outreach and dissemination of project results, communications service provision to RDA WGs, service user and RDA member engagement as part of day to day WG support provided by members of the consortium, etc).

For example, a successful communications campaign at an RDA Plenary involves an exhibition booth, promotional materials with engaging visuals and comprehensive, impactful information; together, these materials attract new service users from the community, who will in turn further engage with the project by joining a WG, submitting an application for RDA TIGER services, etc. In the case of communications as a service to WGs, the WP2 creates and delivers the professional and attractive messaging that promotes the work of the supported WG, in turn maximising its impact, engaging new membership, engaging its key stakeholders, etc.

The sections below will provide an overview of specific methods that WP2 has employed in order to ensure maximum engagement of the community with RDA TIGER (as a service suite, or its supported WGs).

3.2.a. Engagement activities via direct communications

As outlined above, dissemination activities are carried out across the WPs. The activities described here were initially envisaged as WP2 tasks; however, as part of the natural flow of WP5 Facilitation, and as the Facilitators are the primary interfaces between the project and the supported WGs, direct member engagement was 'merged' into Facilitator tasks naturally. Specifically, these activities involve:

- I. Existing contacts (for WGs that are established and have an existing membership): this task involves creating an engagement strategy and ensuring regular and meaningful engagement with the existing RDA WG member base, providing regular updates on meetings, documentation, plenaries, and overall WG work.
- II. 'New' contacts (based on desk research, previous events, etc): This activity, again based on the engagement strategy agreed with WG co-chairs, involves direct

outreach to potential RDA WG members aiming to expand either the member base or to find (new) co-chairs. An example of a strategy that may involve this task is finding membership and/or co-chairs in specific parts of the world, specific disciplines, etc.

3.2.b. Engagement activities via outreach and general dissemination

The tools outlined below are used for 1) service awareness (i.e., engaging new users at the service level within and outside of RDA), and 2) WG work promotion, therefore facilitating engagement of the global research data community with the supported WGs.

Social media

RDA Europe’s [Twitter/X](#) and [LinkedIn](#) accounts are valuable channels through which information about WG activities is disseminated. RDA Europe’s social accounts have relatively high engagement rates compared to [global averages](#), as demonstrated in the analytical reports sampled below. WGs liaise with the RDA TIGER facilitation and communication teams to ensure that their activities/achievements (including endorsement, initiation, Statement of Work development, and recruitment) are promoted via social media throughout the WG lifecycle. Specific engagement takes place through the use of targeted hashtags, highlighting WG mentions and presentations in external events through the RDA channels, etc. (see Figure 2. below).

Figure 2. Social media engagement rates

Email newsletter

RDA TIGER “Research Data Alliance facilitation of Targeted International working Groups for EOSC-related Research solutions” is funded by HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-0 Project: 101094406.

The RDA newsletter, which goes out monthly, is another useful tool for TIGER-supported WGs to disseminate information about their activities and ensure increased engagement with the RDA community. As with RDA Europe’s social media accounts, WGs liaise with the RDA TIGER facilitation and communication teams to ensure that relevant updates are included in the newsletter each month. The RDA Europe communications team then relays these updates to the RDA Secretariat team for inclusion in the newsletter.

EOSC Forum

A valuable tool for the RDA TIGER project is the EOSC Forum, where the team engages with other EOSC-related projects by regularly posting project and WG updates. Given the RDA TIGER supported WGs’ impact on key European initiatives (for example, Semantic Interoperability¹⁴), cross-fertilisation and alignment with other Horizon Europe projects tackling similar challenges is key, and it ensures that key audiences outside of RDA are also part of the overall engagement strategy.

Mailing lists

A number of mailing lists are utilised for targeted user group engagement and dissemination of results, using lists available to the project through the wide RDA networks and its global members at a regional and institutional level.

3.2.c. Events

RDA TIGER Cross-Fertilisation webinar series

The RDA TIGER Cross-Fertilisation Webinar Series is an initiative to enhance engagement and collaboration within RDA TIGER-supported Working Groups. Running during November/December 2024, the series facilitates knowledge-sharing, highlights thematic discussions, and provides opportunities for WGs to identify common challenges and explore further collaboration. The first instalment of the series took place on 27 November and focussed on the theme of Semantic Interoperability. A recording of the session can be viewed [here](#), and the slides can be viewed [here](#). The second instalment of the series took place on 4 December and focussed on the theme of (Meta)Data Standards. A recording of the session can be viewed [here](#), and the slides can be viewed [here](#). The third instalment of the series took place on 18 December and focused on FAIR/TRUST/CARE Adoption. More information on the third instalment is available [here](#) (at the time of writing the recording has not yet been published).

RDA Plenary meetings

WGs are supported to attend and present at RDA Plenary conferences, both virtual and in-person. These meetings provide WGs with an opportunity to showcase their work, recruit new members, and connect with other groups. As well as the supporting the WGs to engage with other RDA Groups and members who may be interested in their plenary sessions and encouraged to join the WG, at the latest RDA Plenary the RDA TIGER Senior Facilitator Ryan O’Connor introduced the RDA TIGER project at the ‘Adoption and Impact of RDA

¹⁴ RDA TIGER Cross-Fertilisation Webinar Series – Semantic Interoperability: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/event/rda-tiger-cross-fertilisation-webinar-series-semantic-interoperability/>

Outputs and Recommendations – Fireside Chats’ session¹⁵, which was open to all attendees. The discussion with the session moderator focused on the progress of the WGs in general, encouraging further engagement with the RDA TIGER project itself and supported WGs.

Service-related informational webinars

These webinars held by the RDA TIGER consortium provide application information and support for the Continuously Open Call for Support Services as well as the Call for Cascade Grants and ensure engagement of new service users. The webinar focussing on the Continuously Open Call For Support Services can be viewed [here](#), and the webinar focussing on the Call for Cascade Grants can be viewed [here](#).

Third-party event attendance

The project consortium attending external events such as EOSC tripartite events, EOSC Symposium, EOSC Winter School, EUDAT, IDCC, EGI and LIBER has been a key instrument for the RDA TIGER project to reach a wider audience outside the RDA, encompassing a large part of the wider European research data community, and informing them of the work and impact of the project as a whole, and of the supported WGs specifically.

Presence at regional RDA events

The RDA Europe team is utilising regional RDA events to engage with the wider European membership. At the time of writing, RDA TIGER services have been presented at and or/discussed in targeted conversations at RDA Netherlands, RDA Slovenia, and in Belgium. RDA Plenary 22 also included dedicated regional sessions, where the RDA TIGER Coordinator presented how RDA TIGER contributes to the regional RDA Europe strategy, further urging engagement with the services and the supported WGs.

4. Information collection

Information collected as part of the Landscape & Engagement Service can be divided into separate tracks along the two main components of the service; information collection for the Landscape component of the service has focused on developing the Landscape Analysis database. These efforts have been described in detail in D3.1 ‘OS Landscape analysis and potential engagement targets’¹⁶ and D3.4 ‘Second OS Landscape analysis and potential engagement targets’¹⁷.

Information collection for the engagement component of the service draws on a combination of the information gathered by the Landscape service, any existing contacts that WG

¹⁵ RDA's 23rd Plenary – Programme and Pathways:

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/rdas-23rd-plenary-programme/>

¹⁶ Rettberg, N., Asmi, A., Molloy, L., Hugo, W., Delipalta, A., & Saldner, S. (2023). RDA TIGER D3.1 OS Landscape analysis and potential engagement targets. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8096612>

¹⁷ Molloy, L. (2024). RDA TIGER D3.4 Second OS Landscape analysis and potential engagement targets. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14017310>

co-chairs may have, and any other target groups, communities or individuals identified by the WG co-chairs and RDA TIGER facilitator, with these comprising a WG’s contacts list. This information is collected using a simple template Excel spreadsheet provided by the RDA TIGER Communications Service. This contacts list is stored in the WG’s own dedicated Google Drive folder, which is set up by RDA TIGER, with access restricted to WG co-chairs, members, and RDA project partners. It varies from WG to WG, but typically this list will contain names, email addresses, organisational affiliation, and additional information such as whether the contact has responded or have indicated they will join the WG. The use of this is primarily at the outset of the WG to track early engagement with the WG’s target audiences; it can also be used to set out the milestones of the WG’s engagement strategy (e.g., what specific target audiences to engage with and when).

Once the WG has been officially endorsed by RDA Council and its area on the RDA website has been set up, it is expected that communications with WG members will all take place via communications mechanisms available on the RDA website. These mechanisms include the RDA website ‘Posts’ function, which essentially acts as a mailing list for everyone who joined the WG on the website. At this stage, it is expected that the contacts list is archived, but retained for reference, with the intention to delete this list at the end of the RDA TIGER project or completion of the WG’s activities, whichever comes first (in accordance with the project’s Data Management Plan¹⁸, the contacts lists will be permanently deleted once the RDA TIGER project ends in December 2025, regardless of whether the WG has completed its activities).

5. Key Performance Indicators

No specific KPIs were foreseen for WP3 as part of the DoA, or initial service definition deliverables; this is because the engagement activities, as established in other sections of this deliverable, are cross-cutting and converge across multiple WPs.

This section will look at tangentially relevant KPIs from other WGs related to engagement.

Table 2. Project-wide KPIs (DoA)

KPI no	Description	KPI	Target	Progress
1	Interest in the RDA TIGER support actions (communication / engagement)	# of applications to RDA TIGER support	30 over the project period	31
2	RDA TIGER WG outputs have high level of interest	Average (over outputs) # of unique	500	Data not available

¹⁸ Asmi, A. (2023). RDA TIGER D1.2: Data Management Plan (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8099103>

	and potential impact (dissemination / WG onboarding)	downloads/views of the outputs/yr during project time		at time of writing due to website migration
3	Landscape follow-up and engagement has provided new members to RDA to participate in the RDA TIGER WGs. (engagement)	# of participants in RDA TIGER WGs, who have not been earlier RDA members	50	Data not available at time of writing due to website migration

Relevant KPIs from WP2

At service definition stage, WP2 KPIs were derived from potential KPIs based on the DoA, and set up with a view that each TIGER supported WG would receive a similar communications package delivered by the WP2 team. In practice, and given that a lot of the engagement-focused activities are carried out by Facilitators, the initial KPIs have not been realistic, especially because WP2 has been a supporting and complementary action to Facilitation.

6. Feedback and service improvement

Feedback on the RDA TIGER project from supported WGs have been positive overall, with all responses indicating that those receiving support have been ‘Satisfied’ or ‘Very Satisfied’ (see Figure 3. Below and ‘D6.4 Report on feedback of the Services and corrective actions’ for detail on the feedback mechanism in place for the project¹⁹). However, as noted above in connection with the delivery of engagement support overlapping with the Facilitation and Communications Services, feedback has focused on the delivery and impact of RDA TIGER services and support overall.

¹⁹ Heikkurinen, M., O'Connor, R., Lehtsalu, L., & Papadopoulou, A. (2024). D6.4 Report on feedback of the Services and corrective actions. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12571122>

Figure 3. Response to question: "Overall, how satisfied are you with the RDA TIGER service you have received/are receiving?"

Some of the feedback which reflected positively on the engagement service noted that the overall support for setting up the WG was "extremely helpful" in connection with "wider reach-out to stakeholders and dissemination" of the WG's activities. Another respondent noted that the support from the Communications Service to produce communications materials for the WG was "very useful in promoting the group and the outputs" to its target audiences. One comment, from a respondent who was "Very Satisfied" with the support from the RDA TIGER services overall, suggested that, if possible, RDA TIGER could provide a funding specifically to support WG co-chairs or members to attend events which are "directly related to outreach and community adoption of RDA developments." This last piece of feedback, and other informal, conversational feedback from other RDA TIGER-supported WGs has fed into the decision to request a small amendment to the initial RDA TIGER project description of work in order to facilitate such a fund for the RDA Plenary 24 meeting due to take place in Brisbane, Australia, in November 2025.

It should be noted here that feedback for RDA TIGER services is sought on a rolling basis; further feedback will be sought from new and existing WGs (both their co-chairs and members) as the project moves into its final year, and this will be used to continuously improve the delivery of the engagement (and all other) services.

7. Conclusion and next steps

The RDA TIGER project will be continuing with its Open Calls for Support into 2025. This means that there will likely be more WGs who will require support from the engagement and other services, in addition to the cohort that the project has already supported. As the project moves into its final year, further refinement of the engagement support will take place; however, given how successful it has been in the previous two years, it is likely that any alterations or amendments to the service will be minimal. The final deliverable for WP3,

'D3.5 – Final report on engagement and landscape monitoring', will look at the Landscape & Engagement service as a whole and will examine what the lessons learned from this will be.

Further success of the engagement component of the RDA TIGER Landscape & Engagement service will reflect the overall concerns for the project in its final year, that is, to support and maximise the impact of the supported WGs' outputs in European and global contexts. The engagement service will be key to this in connecting with potential adopters and implementers of WG outputs; this will also require further collaboration between the Facilitation, Communications, Output Support and Landscape & Engagement services. Having been put into practice in the first two years of the project in support of over 20 WGs, it is hoped that the engagement strategies and activities described above will continue to bolster the overall project needs and aims of the individual WGs.

